

Decoupled Scheduling in Meta Environment

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Abstract—Grid scheduling is the process of mapping grid jobs to resources over multiple administrative domains. Traditionally, application-level schedulers have been tightly integrated with the application itself and were not easily applied to other applications. This design is generic that decouples the scheduler core (the search procedure) from the application-specific (e.g. application performance models) and platform-specific (e.g. collection of resource information) components used by the search procedure. In this decoupled approach the application details are not revealed completely to broker, but customer will give the application to resource provider for execution. In a decoupled approach, apart from scheduling, the resource selection can be performed independently in order to achieve scalability.

Keywords—Meta, grid scheduling, application-level scheduler, decouple, scheduler core and performance model.

I. INTRODUCTION

GRID is a system for management and aggregation of autonomous, heterogeneous, computational and storage resources across geographical and administrative boundaries. Grid computing is a relatively new distributed computing paradigm that is gaining importance. It offers a solution to the increasing demand of highly computational and storage power, without requiring any extraordinary investments in the hardware infrastructure. However, in many cases the grid is not utilized properly without further optimization such as scheduling mechanisms for efficient assignment of application to available resources [4]. So application scheduling is the key issue for deploying parallel and distributed applications at large scale in grid.

For the purpose of application scheduling, the problems of discovering available resources, selecting an application-appropriate subset of those resources, and mapping of data and/or tasks onto selected resources are addressed. This scheduler design seeks flexibility through modularity. And that modules will explicitly *decouple* the scheduler core (the search procedure) from application-specific (e.g. performance models) and platform-specific (e.g. resource information collection) components used by the search procedure. This scheduling approach focuses on minimizing the execution time of a single application on a set of potentially shared resources. This approach has been termed application-level scheduling [2].

II. DECOUPLED SCHEDULING

This section describes the decoupled scheduling approach. To provide context for this description, the detailed scheduling scenario is addressed. A user has an application and wishes to execute that application on computational grid resources. The application is parallel and may involve significant inter-process communication. The target Computational Grid consists of heterogeneous workstations connected by LANs and/or WANs [2]. When the user is ready with the application, the broker is contacted to submit the requirements of the application such as application type, cost and duration. The broker in turn, searches for the suitable resource providers of those requirements submitted by the user and returns the domain address of resource provider to the user. Using the domain address, user will then contact the resource provider. The provider then retrieves CPU speed, memory, cache size and load average from its nodes and calculates the completion time for the given application in all nodes. The least suffered node (least completion timed node) is selected to execute the application.

TABLE I
PROPOSED ALGORITHMS

Algorithms	Description
Dynamic Fastest Processor Task First (DFPTF)	This algorithm provides fastest processors to largest task. It is dynamic and avoids starvation. The metric considered for this algorithm is task size.
Sufferage	This retrieves the least suffering machine for a particular job. Metrics considered are processor speed, memory capacity, cache size and load average.
Max-Min-Max	Both Max-Min and Min-Min algorithms are coupled. This algorithm prefers either large or small application based on number of large or small applications. It is dynamic and the parameter considered for this algorithm is execution time.

III. PHASES OF SCHEDULING

The scheduler performs the following sequential tasks

- **Phase1: Resource Discovery**
- **Phase2: Resource Monitoring**
- **Phase3: Resource Selection.**
- **Phase4: Job Scheduling**
- **Phase5: Job execution**

The scheduler is responsible for resource discovery, resource monitoring and resource selection. During resource discovery, lists of authenticated resources that are available for job submission are identified. In order to cope with the dynamic nature of the Grid, a scheduler will have dynamic state information about the available resources into its decision-making process. The resource selection algorithm is responsible for selecting the resource providers that is capable of executing the application. The scheduling algorithm will make the decisions of which task is to be run in which node under the resource provider. This includes ordering the list of machines in a resource provider for executing the task. The monitoring part handles the issue of fault tolerance by broadcasting the status periodically between the nodes.

Resource Discovery & Monitoring

An information service is a vital component of the grid infrastructure. It maintains knowledge about resource availability, capacity, and current utilization. Within any grid, both CPU and data resources will fluctuate depending on their availability to process and to share data. As resources become free within the grid, they can update their status within the grid information services. The client, broker, and/or grid resource manager uses this information to make informed decisions on resource assignments. The information service is designed to provide:

1. Efficient delivery of state information from a single source
2. Common discovery and enquiry mechanisms across all grid entities

Information service providers are programs that provide information to the directory about the state of resources. Examples of information that is gathered includes:

1. Static host information : Operating system name and version, processor vendor/model/version/speed/cache size, number of processors, total physical memory, total virtual memory, devices, service type/protocol/port
2. Dynamic host information : Load average, queue entries, and so on
3. Storage system information : Total disk space, free disk space, and so on
4. Network information Network bandwidth, latency, measured and predicted
5. Highly dynamic information Free physical memory, free virtual memory, free number of processors, and so on

The Grid Information Service (GIS), also known as the Monitoring and Discovery Service (MDS), provides the information services in Globus. The MDS uses the Lightweight Directory Access Protocol (LDAP) as an interface to the resource information. Monitoring and Discovery Service (MDS): MDS provides access to static and dynamic information of resources. Basically, it contains the following components:

1. Grid Resource Information Service (GRIS)
2. Grid Index Information Service (GIIS)
3. Information providers
4. MDS client

Fig. 1 Grid Scheduling Infrastructures

Globus Resource Allocation Manager (GRAM) is part of the Globus Toolkit used for job submission. The Gram Job Launcher portlet allows a user to submit jobs to a Grid environment using the Globus GRAM protocol. For this the user must have a valid GSI Proxy Certificate which can be loaded through the Proxy Manager Portlet. GIS - Grid Information Service GIS is part of the Globus Toolkit used to manage resources information.

Resource Selection

The scheduler is responsible for finding suitable resource provider. The records of previous applications types met by the scheduler are stored. So that, if any of the application type that is already met by the scheduler comes for the second time, scheduler will allocate the resource provider based on past records instead of searching once again.

If the application comes for the very first time, then application's resources and provider's resources are mapped. If the match exists, address of provider is given to the customer. If the match exists for more than one provider, the tie will be broken using parameters such as job failure rate and bandwidth.

IV. SCHEDULING

A. Resource Broker

Whenever the user wants to execute the application, resource broker is contacted for retrieving the resource provider's address. The resource broker will maintain a policy regarding the acceptance of application based on the cost criteria. Once it accepts the application, a global queue is maintained. The resource provider will provide the complete list of all machines available in grid. Since the grid is a dynamic environment, the broker will watch over the changes in environment and keeps updating.

The algorithm behind the global queue is Max-Min-Max. This algorithm is used for selecting an application from the global queue for allocation. Max-Min [1] is a static algorithm gives highest priority to largest application, whereas Min-Min [1] is a static algorithm which gives highest priority to shortest application. In order to avoid starvation, both algorithms are coupled. This proposed algorithm is called Max-Min-Max algorithm (Since preference is given to max-min algorithm, the name is max-min-max instead of min-max-min) which is described below.

Step 1: Start.

Step 2: Take the execution time of all the application in the queue. Let the number of applications be n.

Step 3: Compute the average execution time (E) that is $E = (\sum \text{execution time})/n$.

Step 4: All application in the queue that has their execution time above E are considered as largest application. (L).

Step 5: All application in the queue that has their execution time below E are shortest application (S).

Step 6: If $n(L) \geq n(S)$ then start with max-min algorithm

Step 7: min-min and max-min algorithm will consecutively alternate it.

Step 8: Else start with min-min algorithm

Step 9: max-min and min-min algorithm will consecutively alternate it.

Step 10: If there are next set of applications go to step2 and repeat the steps 2-9.

Step 11: Else stop.

1) Algorithm Analysis (Max-Min-Max)

TABLE II
ARRIVAL OF JOBS

Jobs	Execution time
J1	10
J2	29
J3	3
J4	7
J5	12

First Come First Serve Algorithm:

$$\text{Average waiting time} = (0+10+39+42+49)/5 = 28 \text{ milliseconds}$$

Max-Min-Max Algorithm:

$$\text{Average waiting time} = (0+3+31+38+40)/5 = 22.4 \text{ milliseconds}$$

2) Pre-Schedule

Broker will maintain three databases for finding suitable resource provider. Records of previous applications types met by the broker are stored in one database (DB1). So that, if any of the application type that is already met by the broker comes for the second time, broker will allocate the resource provider based on past records instead of searching once again.

Broker also maintains all application types along with their needed resources in another database (DB2). Resource provider's information will be stored in another database (DB3). If the application comes for the very first time, then application's resources and provider's resources are mapped. If the match exists address of provider is updated in DB1 and given to the customer. If the match exists for more than one provider, the tie will be broken using parameters such as job failure rate and bandwidth.

Fig. 2 Resource Selection

B. Resource Provider (RP)

Broker will always listen for new providers. When any resource provider comes, they publish themselves to broker. If any of the published resources are in use by local queue jobs, then the corresponding provider will intimate the broker that this resource is not free.

1) Sufferage

Customer now contains the application and provider's address. Within the provider which one is least suffered machine is selected using sufferage algorithm. The metrics considered for this algorithm are CPU speed, free memory, cache size, task size and load average [8]. The result of this algorithm is ordering of less suffering machines within a provider. The algorithm used for scheduling purpose is FPLTF (Fast Processor Largest Task First).

- Step 1: Start
- Step 2: Get the CPU speed, free memory, cache size, and load average of all machine under a selected provider.
- Step 3: Calculate the completion time using formula,

$$\text{Completion time} = \text{TBA} + \text{suffering time.} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Suffering time} = \text{Task size} / (\text{CPU speed} * (\text{free memory} + \text{cache size}) * (1 - \text{load average ratio})) \quad (2)$$

Where, TBA = time for that node to be available.

- Step 4: The customer gives the application in terms of number of tasks along with their sizes. The task with largest size is selected first for scheduling hence framing out Fastest Processor Largest Task First algorithm.
- Step 5: Least completion timed node is selected to execute the application.
- Step 6: Stop.

Fig. 3 Application Scheduling and Execution

Suffering time is directly proportional to task size and inversely proportional to CPU speed, free memory, cache size and load balance. If the processor has more speed, more free memory and cache, more load balance (1-load average) then suffering time for that node to execute the given task is less. If the preferred node is not available or too busy, then head node will allocate the task to next preferred node.

2) Algorithm Analysis (FPLTF)

Fastest Processor Largest Task First

First In First Out

* considering one node for five jobs to execute.

V. CONCLUSION

Thus a decoupled scheduling approach is considered for parallel applications in a computational grid environment. Moreover an exhaustive search of machines in the grid for a similar kind of applications is also reduced, which will lead to less time consumption. And also the performance is evaluated based on the execution time, processor speed, memory capacity, bandwidth, and cache size and load average. Thus the application has been decoupled from scheduling and also dynamic information is exploited at run time for improved scheduling.

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A pre-scheduling concept is used, since the application modules are not revealed to the broker. As per that, the limitation lies here is searching and retrieving more databases. Moreover, when the application comes for the first time, tedious search process will occur, which in turn consumes time. Thereafter when the application comes, this search process can be avoided using pre-schedule

REFERENCES

- [1] "Risk-Resilient Heuristics and Genetic Algorithms for Security-Assured Grid Job Scheduling" Shanshan Song, Kai Hwang, Fellow, IEEE, and Yu-Kwong Kwok, Senior Member, IEEE transactions on computers, vol. 55, no. 6, June 2006 .
- [2] "A Decoupled Scheduling Approach for the GrADS Program Development Environment" Holly Dail, Henri Casanova and Fran Berman, IEEE 2002.
- [3] "Grid Brokers and Meta schedulers Market Overview" Ilona Gaweda and Chris Wilk, Feb 2006.
- [4] "Dynamic Scheduling in Grid Systems" Maria Chtepen, sixth FirW PhD Symposium, Faculty of Engineering, Ghent University, 30th November 2005-paper nr.110.
- [5] "Operating Systems Concepts" Abraham Silberschatz and Peter B. Galvin, fourth Edition.
- [6] "The Anatomy of the Grid" Ian Foster, Carl Kesselman and Steven Tuecke.
- [7] "The Physiology of the Grid-An Open Grid Services Architecture for Distributed Systems Integration" Ian Foster, Carl Kesselman, Jeffrey M. Nick and Steven Tuecke.
- [8] "Trading Cycles for Information: Using Replication to Schedule Bag-of-Tasks Applications on Computational Grids" Daniel Paranhos da Silva, Walfredo Cirne, Francisco Vilar Brasileiro.